

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

C4A

(Complement C4-A)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	720 / POC0L4
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD
TREAT-AD Authors	Emory-Sage-SGC-JAX TREAT-AD Center
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TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a LFQ proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 4) contains several novel targets for Alzheimer's Disease (AD), including CAPN2 and CD44 (1).

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 4.10 (rank #235, 99.1th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 4.10 out of 5 (rank #235, 99.1th percentile). The individual score components include 2.11 of 3 for genetics, and 2 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic For more information or questions regarding the TEP, please contact treatad.info@sagebionetworks.org

and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of C4A, both protein and RNA, is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. The biological domain characterization of the source module (Module 4) indicates that the proteins in this module are enriched for terms annotated to the Structural Stabilization, Lipid Metabolism, and Epigenetic domains. The most significantly enriched terms from this module are “focal adhesion”, “cadherin binding”,

and “membrane raft”. C4A is annotated to GO terms from 5 biodomains, primarily terms from the Immune Response and Synapse biological domains.

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer’s Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence measures of expression. The expression of C4A is not confidently detected in any cell types within this dataset.

Overall	rank	pctl	GeneticsScore	OmicsScore
4.104	235	99.06	2.105	1.999

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

Complement 4A (C4A) scores well in the bioinformatic ranking and could play either a positive or negative role in AD pathology. In order to help the scientific community press forward with the investigation of C4A in AD, we are generating components of target enabling package (TEP) that will be available to the scientific community. Currently, there is no C4A knockout cell line available to validate antibodies to C4A. We hope to be able to provide new scientific reagents for the study of C4A will help drive forward research in the area of AD biology.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Complement 4A (C4A) is a member of the immune complement factor family that is broadly associated with numerous neurodegenerative pathologies. C4A is associated with synaptic loss in schizophrenia (2), a psychiatric disorder with progressive loss of white matter across successive major episodes. One of the fundamental traits of AD pathology, despite not being definitional of the disease, is the loss of synapses over time (3). Both histological studies and synaptic neuroimaging studies have identified the loss of synapses as the component of AD pathology that correlates best with clinical dementia and earlier cognitive decline (4). There are numerous drivers of loss of synapses in AD, including both neurodegenerative loss of neurons, amyloid and Tau pathology converging on dystrophic neurites, and the neuroimmune pruning of the synapses in brain. While immune system synaptic pruning is required for the appropriate developmental wiring of the brain, it is speculated that inappropriate invocation of synaptic pruning by disease associated microglia may be one of the primary elements propelling synaptic loss across disease progression in AD (5). C4A is associated with AD risk, is elevated in expression in AD brains, and can promote synapse loss in AD mouse models (2). C4A copy number variation (CNV) is linked with AD progression and may, at least partially, account for the increase in observed protein levels in AD brain (6). However, a recent study suggest that PP2A and C4A/B interact with the neuroprotective effects of ApoE APOE2 (7). Consequently, C4A may be involved in microglia driven synapse phagocytosis and synaptic decline in AD, yet also be involved in the negative regulation of AD-linked pathology, dependent upon APOE genetic context, potentially making it an interesting AD target, particularly in an APOE4 patient population.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further biological investigation of the role of C4A in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

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ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

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